

EFFECT OF MOTOR IMAGERY TRAINING AND TASK ORIENTED TRAINING ON BALANCE AMONG MIDDLE AGED WOMEN

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Abstract:

Background of the Study: Recent studies found that fall rate has been increasing since from middle age due to the changes in the physiological and environmental factors as it may decrease the ability to maintain dynamic balance and enhances the fall risk among middle age women. The motor imagery training and task oriented training intervention improves the balance and prevent the fear of fall among middle age women.

Aim: To assess the effect of motor imagery training on balance among middle aged women.

Objectives:

- To assess the effect of motor imagery training on fall prevention.
- To assess the effect of motor imagery training on functional balance and gait.

Methodology: This study was an experimental study, which was conducted with 40 participants and were divided into two groups namely experimental group (GROUP A) and control group (GROUP B). Experimental group consists of 20 participants performed the Motor imagery training with the task oriented training and the Control group consists of 20 participants performed the task oriented training with fall prevention education for 45 minutes per day for three times a week for 6 weeks.

Outcome Measure:

- Berg Balance Scale
- Fall Efficacy Scale

Result: The group analysis showed that both Treatment A and Treatment B were effective in terms of improvement in BBS & in terms of reduction in FES-I. However, the final result showed that Treatment A was effective than Treatment B in terms of improvement in BBS & in terms of reduction in FES-I.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the motor imagery training with task oriented training was more effective in improving the balance and fall prevention.

Key Words: Balance, Gait, Fall, Motor Imagery Training, Task Oriented Training.

Introduction:

Fall is defined as an event which results in a person coming to rest inadvertently on the ground or floor or other lower level. Fall related injuries may be fatal or non-fatal though most are non-fatal stated by WHO¹. Fall is considered to be the well-recognized health issues among most of the population in the world². According to WHO, fall related injuries are the second leading cause of disability among worldwide population¹.

Fall related physical changes³, due to ageing which reduces freedom of movements and functional independence direct or indirectly and also affects the mental state of an individual and the psychological changes were leads to increase in fear of fall that affects the functional independence of an individual⁴. The other commonly found risk factors includes the physical performance, physical activity levels, fear of falling, dizziness and environmental hazards⁵.

Other recent studies found that the fall risk is increased in middle age which suggests that one in five middle age adults report having a fall in their lifetime¹⁸. While in comparison with men, women are 58% more likely to suffer from fall and nonfatal fall injury and hospitalizations¹⁹. Falls have been reported to contribute about 40% of the lifetime injury cost for women that may promote a large burden on the public health care system²⁰.

Recently, various interventions have been attempted to prevent falls in the elderly and improve their daily living activities and ability to balance. Among these the Motor imagery training and task-oriented training are being used as evidence-based interventions in diverse fields of rehabilitation^{25,26}. Motor imagery training is a learning process in which the movements are only internally imagined without being physically carried out²⁶. The term motor imagery, also known as 'mental practice', in which the

movements or task is mentally imagined and is learned systematically²⁷. In other words, it is a dynamic state which represent the specific targeted motor action is internally activated without any motor output or execution²⁸. It also requires the conscious activation of brain regions that may involves the movement preparation and execution accompanied by a voluntary inhibition of the actual movement²⁹. This training has been used to promote motor planning and improve upper limb function, mobility and balance³⁰. During the rehabilitation process in older adults the motor imagery training shows the beneficial effect on promoting the motor learning³¹ and enhances the cortical excitability³². And also, the motor imagery training helps to promote the motor planning³³, mobility and balance^{34,35}.

Task oriented training is based on motor behaviour system theory and motor learning. The effectiveness of task-oriented balance training programme in enhancing balance and practice should be trained of controlling the centre of mass regarding the base of support either it is stable or moving³⁰. Task oriented training emerges as an interaction between many systems in the brain and is organized around a goal and constrained by the environment³⁸ and is helpful in improving the balance and self efficacy³⁹. The task-oriented circuit training and progressive resistance task-oriented training are used as effective interventions in the field of rehabilitation medicine^{40,41}.

Aim of the Study:

Aim of this study was to assess the effect of motor imagery training on balance among middle aged women.

Objectives:

- To assess the effect of motor imagery training on fall prevention.
- To assess the effect of motor imagery training on functional balance and gait.

Research Design and Methodology:

An experimental study design was conducted with 40 patients within the age group of 65 to 80 years who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age group 40-<65 years
- Women with MMSE score of >24 points.
- Ability to walk independently and balance.
- Has adequate communication skill.

Exclusion Criteria:

- MMSE score <24 points
- Brain damage or neurological abnormalities
- Visual or hearing ailments
- Treatment with drugs related to walking or balance

Outcome Measures:

- **Berg Balance Scale⁴⁸:** The Berg Balance Scale is used to determine a patient’s ability to safely balance during a series of predetermined tasks. The relative intrarater reliability of the Berg Balance Scale was high, with a pooled estimate of 0.98 (95% CI 0.97 to 0.99). Relative inter-rater reliability was also high, with pooled estimate of 0.97 (95% CI 0.96 to 0.98)
- **Fall Efficacy Scale - International⁴⁹:** Fall efficacy scale-international is a measure of fear of falling or concern about the fall among the population. The FES-I demonstrated high test-retest reliability (intra class correlation coefficient, model 3,1: 0.94; 95% confidence interval, 0.90-0.97)

Procedure:

Table 1: Motor Imagery Training

S.No	Description
1	At the moment you get out of bed at night and walk through the dark room, you lose your balance and are about to fall. At this time, reach out to the wall or the floor to protect your body.
2	At the moment you walk out of the room and sit on the kitchen chair, you are about to fall by mistake. In order not to fall over, reach out and hold the table or wall.
3	When you walk from the kitchen to the living room, there are many items in the house. At the moment you lift one leg to move your foot in order to avoid an item, you lose your balance and are about to fall. At this time, you open your arms to maintain your balance and reach out not to fall.
4	Walk from the living room to the kitchen. Raise your heels to take down an item on the kitchen shelf. At the moment you take down the item, you lose your balance and are about to fall. At this time, in order not to fall, you reach out and hold the kitchen wall or sink.
5	Walk from the living room to the bathroom. At the moment you step into the bathroom, you are about to slip and fall. At this time, in order not to fall, you reach out and hold the sink or wall
6	Go out the front door of the house and go down the stairs. At the moment you walk down the stairs, you lose your balance and are about fall. At this time, in order not to fall, you reach out and hold the stair handrail.

Control Group:

Control group were treated with the task oriented training and fall prevention education were taught to the group and the task oriented training were done for 40 min/day, 3 days/week for 6weeks.

Table 2: Task Oriented Training

S.No	Description
1	Moving a cup while shifting the body weight laterally sitting on a Swiss ball
2	Walk a long a straight line drawn on the floor (5M distance)
3	Moving a long an S-curve while avoiding obstacles (5M distance)
4	Moving water cups
5	Walking up and down stairs
6	Putting a cup on the shelf
7	Replacing bathroom towels
8	Walking on a cushioned mat
9	Maintaining balance while standing on an aircushion and memorizing the words spoken by the researcher
10	Maintaining balance while standing on an aircushion

Inter-Group Analysis (Between Group Analysis):

Comparing the effects of Treatments A and B in terms of change in the value of BBS

- H0: There was no significant difference between Treatments A and B in terms of average improvement in BBS
- H1: There was significant difference between Treatments A and B in terms of average improvement in BBS

The above hypothesis was tested using Independent Samples t-test.

Output of Independent Samplest-test:

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances:

Table 3: Output of Independent Sample T-Test

	A_BBS Diff	B_BBS Diff
Mean	5.2	1.3
SD	2.78	0.66
Variance	7.75	0.43
Observations	20	20
Pooled Variance	4.09	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	38	
t Stat	6.1	
P(T<=t)one-tail	0	
T Critical one-tail	1.69	
P (T<=t) two-tail	0	
T Critical two-tail	2.02	

Graph 1: Mean Improvement in BBS
Mean Improvement in BBS

Result:

There was significant difference between two treatments (A and B) in terms of average improvement in BBS ($t = 6.10$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). In addition, the mean improvement in the value of BBS by Treatment A (5.20) is greater than that of Treatment B (1.30). Hence, we conclude that Treatment A is significantly effective than Treatment B in terms of mean improvement in the value of BBS.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

Table 4: Output of Independent Sample T-Test

	A FES-I Diff	B FES-I Diff
Mean	-5.55	-1.25
SD	1.39	0.85
Variance	1.94	0.72
Observations	20	20
Pooled Variance	1.33	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	38	
t Stat	-11.77	
P (T<=t) one-tail	0	
T Critical one-tail	1.69	
P (T<=t) two-tail	0	
T Critical two-tail	2.02	

Graph 2: Output of Independent Sample T-Test

Result:

There was significant difference between two treatments (A and B) in terms of average reduction in FES-I ($t=-11.77$, $p=0.000<0.05$). In addition, the mean reduction in the value of FES-I by Treatment A (5.55) is greater than that of Treatment B (1.25). Hence, we conclude that Treatment A was significantly effective than Treatment B in terms of mean reduction in the value of FES-I.

Final Result:

The intra-group analysis showed that both Treatment A and Treatment B were effective in terms of improvement in BBS & in terms of reduction in FES-I. However, the inter-group analysis compared the two treatment groups in terms of changes in both the outcome measures and the corresponding result showed that Treatment A was effective than Treatment B in terms of improvement in BBS & in terms of reduction in FES-I.

Conclusion:

The study concluded that the treatment A (experimental group: motor imagery training with task-oriented training) was more effective than treatment B (control group: fall prevention education with task-oriented training) in improving balance.

References:

1. World health organization 2007 WHO global report on falls prevention in older age. World health organization, Geneva.
2. Vaughan Nicholson, Naomi Watts, Yannick Chani, Justin WL Keogh. Motor imagery training improves balance and mobility outcomes in older adults: A systematic review, Volume 65, 2019.
3. Terroso M, Rosa N, Torres Marques A, Simoes R. Physical consequences of falls in the elderly: a literature review from 1995 to 2010. Eur Rev Aging Phys Act. 2014; 11(1):51-9.
4. Dr. Stephanie Studenski, Subashan Perera, Jack Guralnik. Gait speed and survival in older adults, JAMA, 2011; 305: 50-58.
5. Talbot LA, Musiol RJ, Witham EK, Metter EJ. Falls in young, middle aged and older community dwelling adults: perceived cause, environmental factors and injury. BMC Public Health. 2005; 5(1): 86.
6. Falls 2010 Geneva: World Health Organization, media centre, factsheet no: 34, August.

7. Kane RL, Ouslander JG, Abrass IB, Resnick B (2009) Essentials of clinical geriatrics, 6th Edn. McGraw-Hill, New York, pp 265-295, Chapter 9
8. Peterson E, Cho C, Koch L, Finlayson M (2008) Injurious falls among middle aged and older adults With Multiple Sclerosis. Arch Phys Med Rehab 89:1031-7
9. Pinheiro M, Ciconelli R, Martini L, Ferraz M (2010) Risk factors for recurrent falls among Brazilian women and men: the Brazilian Osteoporosis Study(BRAZOS). Cad Saúde Pública Rio de Janeiro 26(1):89-96
10. Formiga F, Navarro M, Duasco E, Chivite D, Ruiz D, Perez-Castejon J, Lopez-Soto A, Pujol R (2008) Factors associated with hip fracture related falls among patients with a history of recurrent falling. Bone 43:941-944
11. Nieuwenhuizen R, Dijk N, Breda F, Scheffer A, Korevaar J, Cammen T, Lips P, Goslings J, Rooij S (2010), Assessing the prevalence of modifiable risk factors in older patients visiting an ED due to a fall using the CAREFALL triage instrument. Am J Emerg Med 28(9): 994- 1001
12. Stel S, Smit J, Pluijm S M, Lips P (2004) Consequences of falling in older men and women and risk factors for health service use and functional decline. Age Ageing 33:58-65
13. Yu P, Qin Z, Shi J, Zhang J, Xin M, Wu Z, Sun Z (2009) Prevalence and related factors of falls among the elderly in an urban community of Beijing. Biomed Environ Sci 22:179-187
14. Coimbra A, Ricci N, Coimbra L, Costallat L (2010) fall in the elderly of the family health program. Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics 51(3):317-322
15. Tirado P (2010) Fear of falling. Rev Esp Geriatriay Gerontol 45(1):38-44
16. Fletcher P, Guthrie D, Berg K, Hirdes J (2010) Risk factors for restriction in activity associated with fear of falling among seniors within the community. J Patient Saf 6(3):187- 191
17. Blyth F, Cumming R, Mitchell P, Wang J (2007) Pain and falls in older people. Eur J Pain 11:564-571.
18. Nitz J C, Choy N L. Falling is not just for older women: support for pre-emptive prevention intervention before 60, Climacteric. 2008; 11 (6):461-466..
19. Ambrose AF, Paul G, Jeffrey M Hausdorff. Risk factors for falls among older adults: A Review of the Literature, May 2013.
20. Nitz J C, Stock L, Khan A. Health-related predictors off all sand fractures in women over Osteoporos Int. 2013; 24(2): 613-621.